

Research information disclosure in the PPMI study: Development of a Disclosure Process

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Introduction

- Disclosure of personal research information to participants in observational studies remains controversial due to ethical and logistical challenges.
- Studies to ascertain participant interest in learning personal research information, evaluating methods of disclosure and counseling, and impact on study outcomes are needed.
- The Parkinson Progression Markers Initiative (PPMI) is a multinational, longitudinal observational study that collects clinical, imaging, molecular, and genetic data from participants with or at risk of Parkinson's disease (PD).

OBJECTIVES

- To ascertain ongoing research information disclosure practice to participants at all PPMI clinical study sites.
- To ascertain PPMI participant interest and input on research information disclosure
- To develop standardized educational content for disclosure of research information with key stakeholder input.

Methods

Part 1: Ascertainment of ongoing disclosure practices

- All site PIs were invited to participate
- A novel survey was created by all authors to collect information on if, how, what type, and by whom research information was being disclosed to participants.
- Email invitations were sent to all PIs with 1 reminder
- Surveys were disseminated between September 22, 2023 and October 13, 2023.
- Summary statistics are reported.

Part 2: Development of educational materials for research information disclosure

- Key concepts for pre-disclosure and post-disclosure education were developed by all authors
- Three content experts developed educational material for alpha-synuclein seed amplification assay (aSyn-SAA), DaT scan, and the Movement Disorders Society Unified Parkinson's Disease Rating Scale Part 3 (MDS-UPDRS-3).
- PPMI participant advisors reviewed the materials Usability Testing:
- Committee and participant advisors reviewed layout, content, presentation, and overall experience and provided feedback to development team, which was incorporated.

Part 3: Survey of Interest in Learning Research Information

Participants: All active clinical participants in PPMI Clinical were invited to participate in this survey.

Methods: 1870 participants were identified and invited to participate by email between 2/13/2024-3/6/2024 with weekly reminders. Participants were asked to respond to 24 questions to learn research information and health literacy.

- 504 (27%) responded to the invitation.
- Summary statistics are reported.

Part 1: Site Survey

Survey Responses:
23/52 sites (44%)

Q1: Is your site currently returning individual research information to PPMI participants?

Q2: If your site is returning research information to PPMI participants, what information?

	Yes
Clinical	12 (75%)
MRI	12 (75%)
DAT	12 (75%)
Genetic	4 (25%)
CSF	6 (38%)
Blood	9 (56%)

Q5: Based on your experience returning individual research information, what information have the PPMI participants been the most interested in receiving?

	Clinical	MRI	DAT	Genetic	CSF	Blood
N (% of 16)	9 (56%)	7 (44%)	11 (69%)	4 (25%)	7 (44%)	4 (25%)

Q3: How is this information delivered?

	In-Person	Phone	Email	Letter	EMR	Other
Clinical (12)	8 (66%)	3 (25%)	1 (8%)	3 (25%)	3 (25%)	2 (17%)
MRI (12)	5 (42%)	3 (25%)	1 (8%)	3 (25%)	4 (33%)	3 (25%)
DAT (12)	6 (50%)	1 (8%)	1 (8%)	2 (17%)	3 (25%)	3 (25%)
Genetic (4)	3 (75%)	1 (25%)	0	3 (75%)	0	1 (25%)
CSF (6)	2 (33%)	1 (17%)	1 (17%)	2 (33%)	3 (50%)	1 (17%)
Blood (9)	3 (33%)	2 (22%)	2 (22%)	1 (11%)	3 (33%)	4 (44%)

Q4: Who returns the information?

	Investigator	Genetic Counselor	Coordinator
Clinical (12)	12 (100%)	0	5 (42%)
MRI (12)	10 (83%)	0	3 (25%)
DAT (12)	9 (75%)	0	4 (33%)
Genetic (4)	4 (100%)	1 (25%)	2 (50%)
CSF (6)	5 (83%)	0	2 (33%)
Blood (9)	6 (67%)	0	4 (44%)

Part 2: Content Development

Part 3: Survey on Interest in Learning

Table (Top). Demographic Summary of respondents.

N	504
Age (avg, SD)	66 y (7.6)
Sex	239M/ 262F
Education	16y (3.4)

Table (Top). Demographic Summary of respondents. **Figure (Right).** Frequency of responses by cohort.

How interested are you in learning your research information?

Figure (Above) Responses pertaining to interest in learning research information. >90% reported they were interested or very interested.

How will learning your information affect your interest in PPMI participation?

Figure (Right) Frequency of responses reporting how learning their research information would affect PPMI participation. No respondents reported 'Less Interested'

Conclusions

- Disclosure of research information is occurring at many PPMI sites (at least 16 of 52 sites), but no standard process exists.
- Clinical, MRI, and DaT scan result are being disclosed by 75% of those sites that return research information.
- Pre-consent, pre-disclosure, and post-disclosure educational material for DaT, MDS-UPDRS Part III, and CSF aSyn SAA was developed on myPPMI, a participant access portal.
- Most participants express interest in learning research information. Learning research information is not predicted to change interest in participating in PPMI.

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